

Turkey – Syria earthquake of 6 February 2023

Coseismic Displacement Map from ALOS-2 Imagery

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This summary report describes a preliminary remote sensing analysis of the coseismic displacement map occurred subsequently the two main event occurred in Turkey-Syria on February 2023.

Two ALOS-2 images along the descending orbit were processed to derive a map retrieved by applying the standard two-steps InSAR approach (Massonet et al., 1998).

The used acquisition dates to form the coseismic pair are:

16/09/2022 and 17/02/2023 for the pre- and post-event acquisition, respectively showing a normal baseline of 48 m and a temporal baseline of 154 days.

Images were in the SCANSAR WD acquisition mode, HH polarisation (Path 77), a multilook factor of 3x25 along the range and azimuth direction was applied resulting in a final ground pixel equal to about 50m x 50m. The ALOS-3D Digital Elevation Model (30 meters) was used to remove the topographic contribution. The Goldstein filtering (Goldstein et al., 1998) was used to filter out possible disturbances and highlight the coseismic fringes. The Minimum Cost Flow algorithm (Rosen et al., 1996) was used to unwrap the phase and remove the residual orbital phase from the interferogram using quadratic polynomial fitting.

Finally, the unwrapped phase was converted into displacement and geocoded in the WGS84 reference system.

Figure 1. Wrapped map of the coseismic interferogram from ALOS-2 data (20220916-20230217).

Each fringe (cycle colour red-blue) represents a ground motion along the sensor Line of Sight equal to about 12 cm.

Figure 2. Displacement map obtained from the unwrapped interferogram.

The retrieved map shows almost the full displacement field of the surface affecting the area after the two mainshocks (yellow stars in the figure). The maximum and minimum motion values are about 2 and -2 meters.

The obtained displacement map confirms the left lateral strike slip regime of the two causative faults.

References

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